

Universität Potsdam

Informed Consent Form for the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

I want to take part in the project PROTEST-AIRT. I consent to the conduction and recording of interviews as well as the processing of my personal data including data revealing my political opinions.

I consent to the transfer of the resulting anonymized transcript of this interview to an open data repository, as part of the open data initiative of the PROTEST-AIRT project.

 YES NO

- **You must be 18 years of age or older to take part in this research study.**
- **You will be given a copy of this consent form for your records.**
- **The interview will be done in English and with your signature you certify that you understand this consent form and that you understand this language.**

Participant Name

Signature and Date

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